
Ayurvedic Treatment in Modern Era in Relation to Ancient System: Challenges and Opportunities

Dr. Sristidhar Bera

Assistant Professor, Gourav Guin Memorial College, Chandrakona Road, Paschim Medinipur

Mail.ID -berasristidhar2@gmail.com

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17597394>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 15-10-2025

Published: 10-11-2025

Keywords:

Detoxification,

Panchakarma, Ayush,

Kopitamala, Samhita

ABSTRACT

The ancient Indian medicinal system known as Ayurveda mostly uses natural substances like herbs for therapeutic effects. It emphasizes on prevention of the disease rather than its symptoms. This is the specialty of Ayurveda. This study tried to focus on 'Ayurvedic Treatment in Modern Era in Relation to Ancient System: Challenges and Opportunities'. The core of Ayurveda is '**Sarveshanam Roganam Nidanam kopitamala**', that means the basis cause of all diseases is the vitiated Mala (waste products or toxins) in the body. According to Ayurveda, maintaining healthy digestion, excretion, and general detoxification is essential for preventing illness and promoting health. First section of this study describes the source ancient Indian medical system, surgery and surgical techniques in sushruta samhita. Charaka Samhita mentions the use of about one lakh Ayurvedic plants for Ayurvedic treatment and the medicinal properties of Ayurvedic plants. Second portion deals with Ayurvedic treatment like detoxification, diet control, Panchakarma, etc. Despite its maximum therapeutic benefits, this Ayurvedic treatment method faces various challenges such as need of scientific validation, quality control and safety concerns, cultural appropriation etc. Integration with modern medicine, great career opportunity, growing demands of natural remedies, vast field of innovation are the opportunity areas appear in last section. The best

side effect-free, Ayurvedic treatment has its roots in ancient Indian Ayurvedic texts and is the key to maintaining physical and mental well-being.

Introduction:

The ancient Indian medicinal system known as Ayurveda mostly uses natural substances like herbs for therapeutic effects. The main tenet of Ayurveda is to find the cause of the disease and cure the patient completely. It emphasizes on prevention of the disease rather than its symptoms. This is the specialty of Ayurveda. Pitta and Kapha doshas have a profound effect on the human body according to the seasons. Similarly, The planet is renewed every autumn as the trees change their shape and shed their old leaves. The cells that provide the body its many organs, systems, and structures its normal operation are called Dhatus.. Juice, blood, meat, fat, bone, marrow and sperm are the seven elements that make up the human body. Ayurveda's three main code of belief are celibacy, food, and sleep. Maintaining this threefold path is very important for leading a healthy life (Verma.et.all 2024).

There is a saying in Ayurveda, ‘**Sarveshanam Roganam Nidanam kopitamala**’. This means that the root cause of all diseases in the body is all the bad substances accumulated in the body. According to Ayurveda, the body may accumulate toxins (Ama) as a result of Malas that are not adequately removed or that are vitiated. This build up interferes with the body's natural energy flow (Prana) and processes, ultimately leading to a variety of illnesses.

Review of Related study:

Pandey, M. M.,et, all (2013) evidenced that The high expense of new medications, the adverse effects of existing treatments, the lack of a cure for many chronic illnesses, microbial resistance, and emerging diseases are some of the factors driving the public's growing interest in complementary and alternative medicine. The Ayurvedic medical system and its function in translational medicine are crucial for treating malnutrition and associated conditions.

Jaswal,Y.S. and Williams, L.L(2016) showed that every individual as the main centre of treatment rather than the disease. Additionally, this issue poses a barrier to the general population's capacity to use drugs.

Katiyar, C. and Dubey, S.K. (2023) postulated that new opportunities for cooperation are created by the growing integration of Ayurveda into traditional medical procedures and wellness strategies. In order to maintain the safety and dependability of Ayurvedic treatments, the complex duties of standardizing and regulating Ayurvedic items and procedures continue to be essential endeavours.

Statement of the problem: After discussing the above reviews, it has been found that no one mentioned ancient Ayurvedic treatment and problems together. An attempt has been made to fill this gap of ancient ayurvedic treatment in the context of modern era. So the title of this study stated as “**Ayurvedic Treatment in Modern Era in Relation to Ancient System: Challenges and Opportunities**”.

Research question:

1. What was the nature of ancient Indian medical science?
2. What was the ancient Indian Ayurvedic treatment?
3. Has Ayurvedic treatment been faced any problem in the context of modern era?

Objectives:

1. To know about the Ancient Indian Medical system;
2. To understand about the ancient Indian Ayurvedic treatment;
3. To understand the challenges and opportunities of ancient Indian Medical system.

Ancient Indian Medical Science

Ancient Indian Medical Science and Treatment mentioned in two Samhitas. Charaka was the father of Ayurvedic medicine and Ayurvedic treatment. He penned a medical treatise called Charak Samhita that described numerous illnesses and provided treatment information.

Sushruta Samhita:- Sushruta is referred to as the "Father of Surgery" because he was a trailblazer in ancient Indian medicine and his achievements have impacted surgery, particularly cosmetic surgery, medical procedures, within the global community. Sushruta discovered about thirty surgical techniques and 20 surgical instruments. His disciplined approach to surgery, including the use of herbal anesthetics and post-operative care, laid the foundation for surgery. Sushruta sets norms that are still the cornerstone of surgical education today with his emphasis on cadavers, hands-on training, and thorough documentation. **Anatomy:** According to Sushruta, becoming a practitioner requires having an understanding of practiced anatomy. In his Samhita, he outlines the entire process. He explained to us

how to use a dead body to learn anatomy; for this, a properly preserved body that is not very old and did not pass away from a serious illness should be used. After examining the body Shushruta Sushruta mentions 500 muscles, 107 articulations, 210 joints, 900 ligaments, and 300 bones (Charak mentions 306). All blood vessels, in his opinion, go through the body.

Ophthalmic surgery: Sushruta was an expert in ocular surgery, which is a specialized procedure used to remove cataracts.

Rhinoplasty: Sushruta in his Samhita mentioned the surgical procedure for rhinoplasty which improves breathing and nasal function and also improve cosmetic look. The first documented account of a forehead flap rhinoplasty can be found in the Sushruta Samhita. He created a new nose by creating a pedicle, a flap of skin from the forehead. Additionally, Sushruta provided a thorough explanation of how to treat six different kinds of dislocations and twelve various kinds of fractures. He also discussed methods for removing undesirable hair and promoting the growth of lost hair. He was among the first doctors in history to propose that a surgical student should dissect a dead body in order to learn about the human body. Sushruta established modern science and discovered various medicines, which are recorded in his Samhita.

Charaka Samhita: Charak opined that the patient's disease will never be cured if a doctor does not go through a patient's body with the lamp of wisdom and understanding. He asserts that a practitioner should be aware of every environmental component that influences a patient's illness. Charak was the first doctor to give the concept of digestion, immunity, and blood circulation. Charaka Samhita mentions the use of about one lakh Ayurvedic plants for Ayurvedic treatment and the medicinal properties of Ayurvedic plants. There are very few adverse effects and little impact on the body's metabolism from the herbs used in Ayurvedic treatments. There are eight divisions and 120 chapters in all. "The science of the causes and symptoms of disease, their treatment, and the maintenance of health" is how it described Ayurveda. The history of medical science, the basic causes of conception and birth, and physical abnormalities are also covered. A thorough categorization, nomenclature, and definition of diseases are included in this treatise (Soni, S. K., & Sharma, S. 2022).

Ancient Ayurveda Treatment:

Detoxification; The process of removing harmful compounds from a living thing, mainly the human body, is known as detoxification. In this process, the body eliminates waste products, toxic compounds, and other undesirable elements with the aid of enemas, diets, and fasting. Drinking alkaline water is a

popular process for detoxifying our body regularly. Because it includes alkaline minerals and is somewhat less acidic than ordinary drinking water, it helps to maintain the body's acidic state since it contains alkaline minerals and is slightly less acidic than regular drinking water. It prevents chronic diseases like cancer, regulates the pH balance of the body, and slows down the aging process.

Herbal Medicine: Natural plant extracts and herbs are used in Ayurveda medicine to treat a variety of illnesses. For the purpose of healing and preserving health, Ayurvedic medicine is made with herbs, mineral-based materials, and animal products. Natural therapies are side effect free treatment than conventional medicine. It has less adverse effect.

Diet and Lifestyle Changes: In order to maintain optimum health, Ayurveda places a strong emphasis on dietary and lifestyle modifications. is determined by the individual's dosha balance and consists of foods that support health and dosha balance. Diet change means well cooked, fresh, good taste thoughtful eating and individualised nutrition. Ideal lifestyle indicates disciplined, systematic daily life, yoga, pranayama, and massage which keep the body in harmony and balance.

Panchakarma: An Ayurvedic detoxification procedure called panchakarma rids the body of pollutants and toxins (Chopra.et.all.2002). It consists of five procedures: Raktamokshana (bloodletting), Nasya (nasal medication), Basti (medicated enema), Virechana (purgation), and Vamana (induced vomiting).

Yoga and Meditation: Yoga incorporates a variety of poses and breathing techniques to support both mental and physical well-being.

Challenges & Opportunities in Present Era:

Challenges:

As individuals search for natural alternatives to traditional medicine, Ayurveda has become increasingly popular in the modern world. We shall talk about the chances and problems that Ayurveda faces in the modern world below.

Need of Scientific Validation: Ayurveda has come under fire for lacking scientific support. The efficacy of many Ayurvedic remedies is not well supported by research, and many have not been examined properly.

Cultural Appropriation: Many Ayurvedic techniques and goods have been commercialized since the Western world acquired Ayurveda. Authenticity and cultural identity have been lost as a result.

Quality Control and Safety Concerns: Many nations do not regulate ayurvedic products, which raises questions regarding their quality and safety. It has been discovered that many Ayurvedic remedies include dangerous ingredients including heavy metals.

Opportunities:

Government initiatives: In india, Ayush is a comprehensive and natural healing method which includes Ayurveda, Unani, homeopathy, siddha, sowarigpa. It has gained the recognition for its time tested practices and therapeutic benefits. Recently it plays an important role in promoting overall well being and diverse treatment options to people.

Rising demand for Natural Remedies: In the modern world, the demand for natural medicine is increasing day by day. People are tired of allopathic medicine. Ayurveda has established itself as the most acceptable, reliable, alternative medicine. A healthy and hygienic medical system can keep everyone healthy.

Integration with Modern Medicine: Ayurveda is a powerful medical system that complements modern medicine. Ayurvedic medicine can be used alongside conventional medical treatment to maintain health.

Increasing line of business Opportunities: Ayurveda offers a wide range of career opportunities. Ayurvedic research, Ayurvedic practice, health counselling.

Huge field for Innovation. Ayurveda has immense research opportunities for the treatment of complex and chronic diseases.

Growing Export Prospect: Many countries in the world today are familiar with Indian Ayurvedic medicine. Countries like China, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, etc. have opened up the opportunity to export Ayurvedic medicines to reap the benefits of ancient Indian Ayurvedic medicine.

Contribution of Ayurveda

1. Ayurveda is a useful approach for managing a variety of illnesses and helping people live healthy lives.

2. As an example of contemporary medical systems, it treats illnesses with natural and herbal ingredients.
3. Ayurveda focuses on an individual's physical and mental well-being.
4. The usage of Ayurveda is widespread throughout the world and has enhanced medical understanding.

Future trends of Ayurveda:

1. Modern science and medical techniques can be combined with Ayurveda.
2. It is a healthy and natural medicinal system that may be advantageous to people.
3. Ayurvedic research and development have the potential to treat more illnesses.

Conclusion: Technological and scientific developments offer a way to authenticate Ayurvedic goods and practices, increasing their credibility and facilitating their incorporation into mainstream treatment. In the modern world, Ayurveda faces a number of opportunities and obstacles, including as safety concerns, cultural appropriation, lack of scientific validation, and quality control issues. Ayurveda, on the other hand, has the ability to enhance contemporary medicine, offer natural substitutes for mainstream care, and open up new commercial and practitioner opportunities.

References:

- Pandey, M. M., Rastogi, S., & Rawat, A. K. S. (2013). Indian traditional ayurvedic system of medicine and nutritional supplementation. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2013(1), 376327.
- Verma, S. K., Pandey, M., Sharma, A., & Singh, D. (2024). Exploring Ayurveda: principles and their application in modern medicine. *Bulletin of the National Research Centre*, 48(1), 77.
- Chopra, A., & Doiphode, V. V. (2002). Ayurvedic medicine: core concept, therapeutic principles, and current relevance. *Medical Clinics*, 86(1), 75-89.
- Sathyanarayana, D., & Snehalatha, J. (2011). Contemporary relevance of ayurveda in complete healthcare system. *International Journal of Research in Ayurveda & Pharmacy*, 2(2), 328-333.
- Renju, S. Chapter-7 Significance of Ayurveda in Current Era.
- Kizhakkeveetil, A., Parla, J., Patwardhan, K., Sharma, A., & Sharma, S. (2024). History, Present and Prospect of Ayurveda. In *History, Present and Prospect of World Traditional Medicine* (pp. 1-72).

- Viswanathan, M. V., Unnikrishnan, P. M., Komatsu, K., Fushimi, H., & Basnet, P. (2003). A brief introduction to Ayurvedic system of medicine and some of its problems. *Indian J Tradit Knowl*, 2(2), 159-69.
- Mann, M., & Pathak, S. R. (2018). Ayurveda: A new dimension in the era of modern medicine. In *Synthesis of medicinal agents from plants* (pp. 283-303). Elsevier.
- Krishna, S., Dinesh, K. S., & Nazeema, P. K. (2020). Globalizing ayurveda-opportunities and challenges. *Int J Health Sci Res*, 10(3), 55-68.
- Saggar, S., Mir, P. A., Kumar, N., Chawla, A., Uppal, J., & Kaur, A. (2022). Traditional and herbal medicines: opportunities and challenges. *Pharmacognosy Research*, 14(2).
- Narayanaswamy, V. (1981). Origin and development of ayurveda:(a brief history). *Ancient science of life*, 1(1), 1-7.
- Charak Samhita, Choukhambha Publication, Varanasi
- Sushrut Samhita, Choukhambha Publication, Varanasi
- Astang Hridaya, Choukhambha Publication, Varanasi
- Soni, S. K., & Sharma, S. (2022). Importance of Ayurved Samhitas in present era.
- Pareek Govind & Sharma Preeti: Importance And Utility Of Samhita In Present Era. *International Ayurvedic Medical Journal* {online} ; c2018 .